

Concept Mapping in Special Education: Current Status and Proposals

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Abstract

The present work refers to concept mapping. In the twenty-first century, the goals of education shifted towards teaching-learning for diverse learning needs. According to research, the field of education is constantly evolving. The study of the international literature was considered appropriate for the investigation of this issue. Conceptual mapping is a pedagogical tool for organizing and representing knowledge (Jonassen, 2000). Conceptual mapping is based on Ausubel's Meaningful learning theory which asserted that new knowledge is constructed from connections to prior knowledge. It enables students with different learning needs as a multiple choice for taking in information and understanding ideas (Dimitrakopoulou, 2001). The purpose of this article, therefore, is to make it clear that in line with the objectives of education, the concept map as a pedagogical tool gives students with different learning needs a multiple choice for taking in information and understanding ideas, and this tool, also, provides a blueprint for teachers to improve and develop the learning environment through multiple representations of concepts.

Keywords: Concept mapping, Students with special needs, Special education, Methods of construction, Positive effect, Recommendations.

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1. Introduction

On the threshold of the twenty-first century, technology, with the help of educational software, has helped to change the way schools teach. In particular, educational software for constructing and editing concept maps has raised interest in their concept maps (Ortega and Brame, 2017) [1]. Their pedagogical value lies in the fact that on the one hand they function as teaching tools, assisting the teacher's work, and on the other hand as learning projects` thus, as activities for students and as tools for teachers to assess their own learning (Safdar, Hussain, Shah, Rifat, 2012) [2].

Conceptual mapping is a visual thinking skills strategy often used in educational processes. It shows various relationships between concepts (Novak, 1990) [3]. It is useful for identifying key concepts presented in a lecture or text. A concept map is created as a tree-like structure, with the most comprehensive concept at the top and the most important ones connected by lines to the first concept. The concept mapping can be created either on paper or using various software.

Conceptual mapping is an innovative strategy in teaching and learning, which has recently emerged and developed to support critical thinking in the form of knowledge representation (Jonassen, forthcoming) [4]. The use of this method allows for the activation of both parts of the human brain that enhance memory and creativity, and is also highly effective in managing complex information (Bowen & Meyer, 2008) [5]. In school curriculum courses, it is argued that concept mapping is an effective way of teaching that can arouse the interest of all students, including students with different difficulties, and lead to improved learning. Thus, the teacher can use this strategy in order to identify important concepts and their relationships, reinforce the meanings of the relationships and demonstrate clear understanding (Stoica, Moraru and Miron, 2011) [6].

Consequently, it is evident that learning is not a simple transfer of knowledge from teacher to learner, but the result of a process of personal construction of knowledge through combining new information with existing knowledge and adapting new ideas and knowledge to existing ones (Brooks J.G., Brooks M.G., 2001 [7]; Shapiro A., 2002) [8].

2. Concept mapping

Concept mapping is a graphical representation of the relationship between terms (concepts). It is a method that usually encloses concepts in circles or boxes of some type, and the relationships between them with connecting words. The linking words identify the relationship between the two concepts. A pair of concepts is connected by a one-way arrow, and the arrow is connected by a word or short phrase that describes the relationship between the two connected terms. These linked terms can be read as a sentence. According to Novak & Gowin (1984) [9], "concept maps are intended to represent the meaningful relationship between concepts in the form of sentences". Novak also defines "concept" as a perceived regularity in terms or objects, characterized by a label.

An important point is that there are two important features of concept maps in the representation of creative thinking: the first is the hierarchical structure. At the top of the map the most general concepts and the most specific concepts are hierarchically fixed below, and the second is the "cross-connections". This helps us to identify and understand how certain words represented on the map are connected to each other. Another important feature also is examples and pictures of events or objects to clarify the meaning of a concept. In general, it is a tool for organizing and representing knowledge to form a meaningful statement. For this reason, the map should be structured by a focus question for a specific knowledge domain. In addition, other techniques, such as the usual method of note-taking, do not allow important points to emerge and do not adequately show the relationship between ideas. Consequently, they do not have positive results, especially for students with special educational needs. On the other hand, cognitive mapping is a popular technique, invented (and) developed by Tony Buzan (1995) [10], in England. Studying the workings of the brain, the British psychologist recommends that people should not take linear notes by writing down word for word what they hear or read, because the brain does not work that way. Information is stored in the brain's dendrites, such as patterns, connections and associations. For this proposal, Buzan (1995) [10] suggests the technique of conceptual mapping because the "conceptual map" method develops memory, shows connections between related points and

thus maintains the interest of students with special needs.

Moreover, in terms of concept maps, there are four types. The first is the Spider Diagram. The main concept is placed in the center of the map and the sub-concepts are organized around the center along lines that run outward to create a diagram similar to a spider web. The second type is Hierarchy concept maps, in which the most general concept is at the top of the map and the more specific ones are organized following a downward scaling. Another type is conceptual flowchart maps in which concepts are organized in a linear mapping. Another final type is conceptual system maps where information is organized in a flowchart-like format with the addition of input and output. Complementarily, there are three additional types of concept maps. The first type is Picture Landscape concept maps that present concepts in landscape form. The second type is the multidimensional /3-D conceptual maps, which are used in case dimensional maps are not sufficient` and the last one is the Mandala conceptual maps where the concepts are in the form of interlocking geometric shapes (Dimitrakopoulou, 2001) [11]. Consequently, the teacher can choose one of these types and use them as a basis for organizing his lesson in order to achieve a vital impact on all his students, including those with learning difficulties.

In summary, the most common way of constructing a concept map is "paper-pencil" or in Post-It notes. In recent years, computational tools have been developed both at the commercial level, such as Inspiration² [12], Axon Idea Processor (MahyarNarges, 2008)[13], and at the research level, such as CmapTools³[14] (Cañas et al., 2004)[15], CM-ED (Concept Map Editor) (Rueda et al., 2006)[16] and COMPASS (Gouli et al. 2006)[17].

2.1 Educational Theory of Concept Maps

Conceptual mapping is based on Bruner's constructivist theory, which is seen as an active learning process in which students construct new ideas or concepts based on their current or prior knowledge. Concept maps were developed by Joseph D. Novak and his research team at Cornell

University in the 1990s as a way of illustrating the construction of scientific knowledge in children. It was then used as a tool to enhance science learning and various areas not only in education but also in other areas, for example, in government and vocational programs. This program was based on David Ausubel's psychology of learning (1963, [18] 1968, [19] 1978 [20]). His theory is the theory of assimilation, according to which the most important factor for learning is past knowledge. In addition, Ausubel made a major distinction between memorization and meaningful learning. For there to be meaningful learning, firstly the learning material must be conceptually clear with examples in the learner's prior knowledge. Thus, concept maps can help to achieve this goal. Second, the learner must choose to learn meaningfully. This occurs when the teacher motivates students to learn by incorporating new concepts into their prior knowledge rather than just memorizing definitions of concepts. Consequently, concept maps are not only a learning tool but also an assessment tool, thus encouraging students to use conceptual learning models (Novak & Gowin, 1984 [9]; Novak, 1990 [3]; Mintzes, Wandersee and Novak, 2000 [21]). Furthermore, according to Huberman (1990) [22], knowledge acquisition is a process of interaction with the environment, a collaborative process. On top of this process, the creation of conceptual maps is founded. Similarly, in concept mapping, knowledge is built through an interactive connection between participants and the outcome, so that it is a visual representation of the understandings built during people's social interaction (Jonassen, 2000) [23]. Finally, the use of mediating cognitive tools, structured in a flexible and harmonious way to help bridge the gap and promote the concepts of scientific knowledge and to be a scaffolding for the Zone of Proximal Development, so as to transform learning into a stress-free, easy and natural process, taking into account the social and cultural environment (Vygotsky, 1986 [24]; Jonassen, 2000 [23]), has become a paramount requirement. Referring to the Zone of Approachable Development, is the process when students work collaboratively in groups and use concept maps to guide their learning, significantly greater learning occurs (Preszler, 2004) [25].

²URL: <http://www.inspiration.com/home.cfm> [12]

³URL: <http://cmap.ihmc.us> [14]

2.2 Concept mapping in educational contexts

In the process of learning, the teacher should be interested in teaching students in a way that they contribute as much as possible to the acquisition and organization of new knowledge, so that they retain and recall it when needed (Reigeluth, 1983) [26]. Conceptual mapping is an extremely important tool for the educational process. It is useful for representing knowledge in any scientific field and for organizing and understanding new subject matter. Thus it is useful for teaching and assimilation of knowledge by the learner.

As far as teachers are concerned, concept maps can be used, first of all, as a tool for organizing the content of the lesson. Thus, it helps the teacher to clarify the course of instruction and present it more effectively (West, Farmer & Wolff, 1991). [27] Specifically, the concept map can be used both to present the topic related to the key units and to present a lesson plan in which the objectives, content, teaching techniques and teaching aids are reflected. Secondly, it can be used as a diagnostic tool. With this instrument the teacher can achieve the detection and reconstruction of prior knowledge. Consequently, it is very important because the teacher is able to examine how well a student understands the lesson, identify misconceptions and adjust teaching techniques to facilitate the acquisition of new knowledge by reconstructing existing knowledge (Vosniadou, 1994) [28]. Thirdly, the concept map can be used as a tool to provide the teacher with information about the development of cognitive change in students and the final outcome of his/her teaching. Fourth, concept maps present a number of advantages by facilitating the learning process and contributing to knowledge retention. In summary, in my opinion, taking advantage of these benefits allows teachers to achieve optimal results and goals they set for their students' instruction so that they can be more successful in helping their own students learn meaningfully.

In addition, as far as students are concerned, concept maps are a beneficial tool because they can be used by students: on the one hand, firstly, as a practical way to take notes during the delivery of a lesson, and, secondly, as a way of keeping them as a practical tool to help them to keep a record of the concepts they have learned in class. On the other hand, firstly, as a way of learning the concepts better and more effectively

to be taught, and secondly, as a mechanism to extract as initial ideas and assist in the organization of ideas. Moreover, the use of concept maps can achieve many benefits for students (Papathanasiou, Lympouridou and Savvas, 2002) [29]. The first of these is effective learning. In the process of designing the maps, because of the step-by-step method followed, it is easy to achieve a full understanding of the meaning of the concepts, as well as the relationships between them, because students have the opportunity to think about the connections between the terms they are learning and organize their thoughts to visualize the relationships between the concepts in a systematic way, reflecting on their understanding. Consequently, Learning is an active process. The second is creative thinking. By engaging in brainstorming and putting their ideas on paper without criticism using brainstorming criteria (Osborn, 1948) [30], ideas are clearer and the mind is freer to grasp new ideas. These new ideas can connect with existing ones and trigger new connections that will lead to other ideas. In addition, the third benefit is increased "metacognition". Map concepts are tools that help students understand the structure of knowledge and the process of knowledge construction. Thus, they help them "learn how to learn." and require students to work at all levels of Bloom's (1956)[31] pyramid (knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation). In addition, the fourth benefit is the cultivation of critical thinking through phases of generating and organizing ideas and revising and reformulating the original text (Matsangouras and Kouloubaritsi, 1999) [32]. Finally, the fifth is the enhancement of group learning. A concept map represents the group's ideas. According to Novak & Gowin (1984) [9], it is a communicative communication tool between group members, who elicit their thoughts on the topic when discussing their maps each other and also a tool to negotiation of meaning. This also enhances the interaction between members of the group and reinforces learning (Matsangouras, 2000) [33], as well as being a method of problem solving. In conclusion, it is confirmed that this method has become an important tool to help students learn to learn meaningful learning and help teachers become more effective teachers, as well as changed their view of the curriculum - with significant implications for teaching and learning.

3. Concept mapping in Special Education in Greece

According to Novak (2010) [34], in the past decade, there has been tremendous growth of the WWW, low-cost, largely increased computer capabilities and increased Internet bandwidth. These capabilities provide a new way of organizing and delivering learning experiences that allow for the coordinated and integrated use of all instructional approaches in a new synthesis that researchers call the New Model for Education. A of the ideas introduced in the New Model is the use of the "expert skeleton" conceptual maps that serve as a starting point. O'Donnell, Dansereau, & Hall (2002) [35] have shown that "knowledge maps" can serve as scaffolding to facilitate learning. In particular, the second version of the Learning, Creating, and Using Knowledge further describes the New Model and their also provides additional examples where efforts are being made to implement this model in school settings (Novak & Cañas, 2006a) [36]. Although Bowen and Meyer (2008) [5] have shown how the New Model has helped, at this time still implementation of the New Model is still in its infancy.

Conceptual mapping has been used in the educational process in various disciplines, such as environmental education and science teaching, and at various levels of education. In some research studies, conceptual mapping has been used as a tool to explore students' prior knowledge (Pearsall et al., 1997) [37], as a tool to explore students' representations of the subject matter (Kollias et al., 2000) [38], as a collaboration tool (Basque and Lavoie, 2006) [39], as a tool for conceptual change and assessment (Mintzes et al., 2000) [21], and as a problem-solving tool (Lee and Nelson, 2005) [40], as well as in special education.

In order for conceptual mapping to become an integral part of the special education process it is necessary to design activities that may involve familiarizing students with this method and utilizing this method as a teaching tool, as an assessment tool and as a tool for challenging student interest and active participation. The activities of concept mapping, according to the results, can be associated with a variety of projects. For example, constructing a concept map is classified as a low-degree help or guidance task, but completing the concept map is classified as a high-degree task. During these tasks, students

may have a concept park or global questions. According to researchers, administering the concept parking may limit the creativity of struggling students, but it allows the teacher to discover different specific difficulties and problems students have with these concepts (Novak and Canas, 2006) [41], and to resolve them.

Despite the rich literature and the interest of the scientific community in the use of this method in special educational practice, its use in Greek education is quite limited (Gkouli, Gogoulou, Papanikolaou and Grigoriadou, 2005) [42]. The educational processes are usually carried out through suggestions and questions, so that the active participation of students is limited and does not facilitate the clarification and understanding of concepts. Moreover, based on the studies and teachers' experience opinions, when applying concept mapping, students face several difficulties in identifying the concepts to be depicted on a concept map, as well as determining the connections between the concepts. For this reason, students with learning disabilities need a period of familiarization with key concepts in order to construct a proper concept map.

4. Methods of construction of concept maps

The technique of concept mapping is a valuable tool through which any individual - typical or disabled - or group of people can organize their thoughts in a creative and innovative way; or even summarize another person's notes as expressed in a book, an article or a lecture. Although the concept mapping method can be used in a large number of applications, this article is concerned with the use of concept maps exclusively in special education.

The following steps are the ones (Jonassen et al., 1993) [44] provides for creating concept maps for students and for anyone who wants to create a concept map:

- **Step 1:** Create a plan and define the perspectives for analyzing an educational object. Students with difficulties need to make a plan for the concept map, about what they want to present, what points they want to highlight, what information they need to create these points, what learning objectives they need to achieve. Thus, through their concept maps,

students with disabilities can take notes and organize their materials during the lesson.

- **Step 2:** Defining important concepts. For proper understanding in something, the main role is the concept to be used. Through experience in creating concept maps, students with disabilities can identify for themselves the main concepts that exist in books or other educational materials. According to Yin et al. (2005) [43], one of the most important steps in creating a concept map is selecting the central idea and key terms. In this way, the teacher can find connections in the lesson material as well as in the ways of communicating it to children.
- **Step 3:** Creating, defining and configuring the nodes. For each concept, we create a node. Then we add pictures and explanatory texts. A picture also automatically focuses the eye and brain, creates great coherence and is effective as a memory aid.
- **Step 4:** Create links between the concepts. The process of creating these links requires research into the variety of possible relationships to define this study. Concept mapping is formalism for representing structural knowledge (Jonassen et al., 1993) [44]. Structural knowledge, the understanding of these relationships, allows students with disabilities to form the connections they need to use scripts or schemas. Structural knowledge has been conceptualized and described by several authors (Preece, 1976[45]; Tennyson and Cocciarella, 1986[46]). In addition, concepts are related to each other in many ways, depending on the text in which. The lines that connect the central idea are more pronounced because they immediately convey the brain weight of the central ideas.
- **Step 5:** Expanding the concept map. Organizing and sorting improves clarity and aids in retrieval. In this way, the teacher can show the connections between the lesson definitions. Through their concept maps, students with learning

disabilities can also take notes and organize their materials during the lesson.

- **Step 6:** Students with special needs continue the process. They continually review the concept map and monitor its development and the progress of its goals. Thus, they continue to reflect on the meaning of the terms. If students with different difficulties finish their work, it is good to critique what they have learned about the content of the concepts, working with others, essentially expressing the evaluation criteria defined by the students themselves for the whole process. In addition, with the help of concept maps, students with special needs can develop the ability to understand how it is possible to relate different topics of the lessons.

5. Positive effect of concept maps

Conceptual mapping plays a key role in the educational activities of the course and, together with other metacognitive tools, helps students to take responsibility for their own meaning (Novak, 1985) [47]. This open-minded activity is highly preferable because it reflects differences in students' cognitive structures and elicits higher-level cognitive processes, not only in general education but also in special education.

According to Dimitrakopoulou (2001) [11], there are some positive effects of conceptual mapping. One important effect is that concept maps individualize the learning skills of all students, typical students and students with special needs. The manipulability of the representation allows for revisions and corrections, which leads to better mastery of the subject matter and contributes to metacognitive, metacognitive awareness. These tools emphasize the meanings of key concepts and principles in ways that students can form a conceptual understanding of the topic. In this way they will become skilled in using the metacognitive tools. Another benefit is that this method facilitates the development of thinking. Students become producers and transformers of knowledge. Thus, this map also enables the understanding of complex terms. In addition, the concept map is used as a teaching tool to detect students' pre-knowledge, as an assessment tool and a self-assessment tool that increases students' self-regulation and self-efficacy. In conclusion,

students with learning disabilities in a classroom using concept mapping rather than conventional lecture received high scores because concept maps address the critical issue of how they organize their knowledge structures within and across domains. Thus, the way in which they represent and apply knowledge (Jonassen and Marra, 1994) [48].

In summary, open-ended activities are preferable for students with disabilities because they provide more opportunities for students to determine their conceptual understanding and provide greater scope for demonstrating students' partial understanding and misconceptions. In general, a carefully designed concept map activity can be a beneficial asset that any student, typical or with disabilities, can have.

5. Concluding remarks and recommendations

Meaningful learning is one of the primary goals of education and can be achieved through the active participation of the learner, and especially the learner with special needs, in activities aimed at the gradual construction of knowledge, based on what he or she already knows within a friendly, social and cultural context (Fardanesh, 2002 [49]; Mayer, 2002b [50]). Consequently, the use of these maps helps to improve the learning and performance of all students, whether typical students or students with difficulties in the areas of text comprehension/reading, thinking and learning skills (organizing and communicating ideas, observing patterns and relationships, categorizing ideas), retaining and recalling knowledge over a long period of time, and problem solving.

However, although conceptual mapping is easy to use and learn, constructing conceptual maps remains a complex and complicated process. As a result, it eliminates some limitations such as lack of appropriate knowledge on how to construct concept maps and insufficient experience in using concept maps. Thus, it is a prerequisite to train special education teachers to learn how to construct concept maps and how to use them correctly and effectively helping to provide special teaching and enhance learning. Another possibility is for students with disabilities to learn how to use and construct concept maps before the research begins. This will eliminate the frustration expressed by students with lower abilities in

constructing concept maps (Pendley et al. 1994[51]; Lee and Fensham 1996 [52]).

In addition, further research could be conducted to attribute a number of factors required for the proper utilization of concept mapping. They are: the first is the duration of the experimental investigation (six 50-minutes periods). It should be carried out over a longer period of time in order for students with special needs to better understand the new concept mapping technique. The second factor is the number and heterogeneity of students in each class. In addition, the third is the skills of the teacher. The fourth factor is the quality of the tests. In addition, the fifth is the quality of the lessons. The last two factors are the quality of the conceptual maps presented and, finally, the quality of the visualization techniques used. Thus, the concept maps method could be used in the teaching of vocabulary and reading in special classes and the role of concept maps in the teaching of higher level cognitive skills (application-analysis-synthesis) could be investigated.

In summary, conceptual mapping is a powerful cognitive tool that supports the special education process by promoting new learning goals such as high-level cognitive skills (problem solving, collaborative work on complex projects) and metacognitive skills that allow the special needs student to control the learning process (Dimitrakopoulou, 2001) [11].

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